

HAVING TO DIRECT THE PROHIBITED MEDICATION AND OTHERS IN CASE OF ILLNESS

الاضطرار إلى مباشرة المحظور من الأدوية وغيرها في حالة المرض

Abul Firdaus Bayinat Basha Al-Bajali*

*Department of Quranic Sciences and Interpretation College of Islamic Sciences Al-Madinah International University / Malaysia, abulfaradeeatnet@yahoo.com abulfaradees11@gmail.com

أبو الفردوس بينات باشا البجالي

قسم علوم القرآن والتفسير كلية العلوم الإسلامية جامعة المدينة العالمية / ماليزيا

***Corresponding Author:**

abulfaradeeatnet@yahoo.com, abulfaradees11@gmail.com

Abstract

Worship includes every human movement in life. Based on this, a person's quest to take care of himself and his society is an obligatory matter, and he is rewarded for it as long as he adheres to what he must do in it. The research has been called having to engage in prohibited medicine and other things in case of illness; because the meaning of compulsion is a comprehensive meaning that touches on many matters, and a person must be characterized by reconciliation with himself and with others. I have dealt with in this research some of the provisions of necessity in a number of the following issues:

- The ruling on healing and treatment between a man and a woman
- Prohibited medication
- Using the organs of the dead to treat the living

Then I interpreted the verses and explained the hadiths, criticism and deduction, and listed the opinions of the scholars and tried to explain the most correct one. Using the analytical method, then it showed the teachings to which the verses guide us, which must be applied in dealing with people through the applied approach.

Keywords: compulsion, direct, forbidden, valleys, disease.

ملخص البحث

إن العبادة تشمل على كل حركة من حركات الإنسان في الحياة، وعلى هذا فإن سعي الإنسان إلى العناية بنفسه ومجتمعه أمر واجب، وهو مأجور عليها ما دام يلتزم بما يجب عليه فيها، وقد سميت البحث بـ **الاضطرار إلى مباشرة المحظور من الأدوية وغيرها في حالة المرض**؛ لأن معنى الاضطرار معنى شامل يتطرق إلى أمور كثيرة، والإنسان يجب أن يتصف بالإصلاح مع نفسه ومع غيره، ولقد تناولت في هذا البحث بعضاً من أحكام الاضطرار في عدد من المسائل الآتية،

- حكم المداواة والعلاج بين الرجل والمرأة
- التداوي بالمحرمات
- استعمال أعضاء الميت في معالجة الحي

ثم قمت بتفسير الآيات وشرح الأحاديث والنقد والاستنباط وصرده آراء العلماء ومحاولة بيان الراجح منه. مستخدماً المنهج التحليلي، ثم بينت ما ترشد إليه الآيات من تعاليم يجب العمل بها في التعامل مع الناس من خلال المنهج التطبيقي.

Having to direct the prohibited medication and others in case of illness:**The first requirement: the ruling on healing and treatment between a man and a woman****Ruling on uncovering, looking and touching:**

In the case of illness for the purposes of examination and treatment, it is permissible to examine the return and the doctor's examination, except for what it is not permissible for him to look at from the body of a woman or a man out of necessity. Examples of what the jurists have stipulated regarding the estimation of necessity is what Imam Al-Suyuti mentioned in his likes: "If a stranger intended for a woman, he must cover all her forearms and not reveal anything except what is necessary for her to be exposed, and in a cast, he must not cover the right part except what is necessary. ". However, this permission and licensing should not be granted for the treatment of women by the man and the treatment of men by the woman, unless there is no woman who is knowledgeable in matters of medicine and treatment. If there is no woman who is knowledgeable in matters of medicine and treatment, or if she is found and has little knowledge of matters of treatment, it is permissible for the woman to be treated by the man, and what we have said of looking and touching is permissible for him as much as is necessary calling for treatment without exceeding this limit, otherwise the matter will turn back to its origin, which is the prohibition. It came in Al-Mabsout by Imam Al-Sarkhasi Al-Hanafi: "If a woman afflicts a sore in a place where it is not permissible for him to look. Learn that if you know and they fear that she will perish or suffer a calamity or pain she cannot bear, there is nothing wrong with them covering everything from it except the place of that ulcer, then a man will heal it and lower his gaze as much as he can except from that place, because looking at a sex other than sex is more severe, so it is considered that the necessity and that Because of the fear of doom for her, and at that time, it is not permitted except to the extent that the necessity increases.." And similarly it came in the Indian fatwas: "It is permissible to look at the vagina of the circumcised, midwife and doctor when treating and lower his gaze as much as he can. .

And it came in the book Al-Hedaya by Al-Marginani: "It is permissible for the doctor to look at the place of the disease in it for necessity, and he should teach a woman to treat it, because looking at sex is easier, and if they are unable to cover every part of it except the place of the disease, then he looks and lowers his gaze as much as he can, because what It is established by necessity that it is estimated according to its value, and it became like the sight of the lowered eye and the circumcision..." Al-Jahiz said in Al-Fath: "It is permissible to treat foreigners when necessary, and it is estimated according to its value in terms of looking, feeling with the hand and so on. Ibn Muflih said in the Book of Shariah Etiquette: Other than a man, it is permissible for him to see from her what is necessary to look from her, even the vulva, and the same is true for a man with a man.." Ibn Hamdan said: "If there is no one to treat him except a woman, then she has the right to look at what is necessary for her to look even to his private part."

The judge said: "It is permissible for a doctor to look at a woman's private parts when needed, and it is also permissible for a woman and a man to look at a man's private parts when necessary." It came at the beginning of al-Mujtahid to Ibn Rushd that he slandered women from the booty and said: "The public became to the fact that the woman does not divide her and accept it." So that Umm Atiyah is the firm, as they used to go out with the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, to treat the wounded and nurse the sick. No?. They agreed that women are permitted to invade..." And in the profound argument of God for Al-Dahlawy: "He should submit, without the arrow, to women, to treat the sick, to cook food, and to set right the affairs of the invaders..." In Al-Mughni by Ibn Qudamah al-Hanbali, he said: "As for The old woman and she is the oldest, if there is a benefit such as watering water and treating the wounded, then there is nothing wrong with it, because we have narrated from the news, and Umm Sulaym and Nusaybah bint Ka'b were raiding with the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace. We go out with the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, to give water and treat the wounded Anas said: The Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, was going to battle at Umm Sulaym and some Ansar women with her, giving water to the wounded and treating the wounded. If it is said that the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, used to go out with him from among his women, and he went out with Aisha several times. It was said that this is one woman who takes her when he needs her, and the same is permissible for the prince when he needs her." This is a summary of the opinions of the jurists of the four well-known schools of Islamic jurisprudence on the issue of the treatment of a man by a woman, and the treatment of a woman by a man in case of necessity. The permissibility of this in case of necessity. But if we move to the purified Sunnah of the Prophet, we will find a lot of that in Sahih Al-Bukhari: Khalid bin Dhakwan told us on the authority of Al-Rabi' bint Mu'adh bin Afra who said: "We used to go on an expedition with the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, watering the people and serving them, and returning the dead and wounded to Al-Madina" and this hadith was mentioned under the chapter "Does a man treat a woman, and a woman a man?" Al-Bukhari mentioned in another section "the chapter on the treatment of wounded women in an invasion." By hand, and so on, and in Sahih Muslim, there are many hadiths that confirm that. On the authority of Umm Attia al-Ansari, she said: I made an expedition with the Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him. true p On the authority of Anas bin Malik, he said: The Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, used to invade with Umm Sulaym and women from the Ansar with him, if he invaded, they would give water and treat the wounded." In Sahih Muslim on the authority of Anas. On the day of Hunayn, Umm Salim took a dagger. The Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, said to her, What is this dagger? She said, "I took him if one of the polytheists approached me, and his stomach softened, so the Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, made him laugh.." In case of necessity, the necessity pays its amount without any increase. God knows.

The second requirement: the treatment of taboos

Ruling on taking alcohol:

Wine is the mother of evil things, and it destroys money, degrades the mind, suppresses manliness, and degrades the body. And it is that which brings the body the hidden disease and the crippling disease, and it is the one that destroys life, damages nerves and fibers, and destroys immunity and resistance. And if some doctors neglect the matter of religion in this regard, describing wine as a cure for a sick person as a temporary sedative, or a temporary covering for the disease, then this is from not seeing the subtleties and secrets of medicine and from the weakness of the soul that must try between religion and medicine.

Modern medical research has proven that there is no disease in which alcohol is used as a treatment, unless there is another medicine instead of alcohol that can take its place and avoid its bad consequences. And if the doctors themselves, who were given insight into the delicate matters of their profession, and the secrets of their glorious craftsmanship, decide this, then they serve the community, the living, and the religion. Why then resort to the use of alcohol in medicine? It is surprising that the illiterate Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, whom God sent hundreds and hundreds of years ago, makes an eloquent miraculous sign. He says in more than one hadith, for example: The hadith narrated by Abu al-Darda' said: The Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, said: "God sent down disease and medicine and made for every A disease is a medicine, so seek medical treatment and do not take medication with forbidden." Ibn Masoud said in Al-Munkar: "God has not made your healing in what He has forbidden you..." Al-Bukhari mentioned this and the jurists have sayings about medication with alcohol summed up in two doctrines:-

The first doctrine of the majority of jurists:

A large group of jurists went to the prohibition of drug treatment, whether it is from food or drink, especially alcohol. In the treatment of drinking it must limit. Rather, the Malikis were of the view that it is also not permissible to take medication with it by drinking, even if he fears death for himself. Among those who agreed with this were the Hanbalis, Shiites, and Imamis, and a view in the Shafi'i school and Muhammad ibn al-Hasan al-Shaybani of the Hanafi school, and in this opinion, these jurists unanimously agreed on the prohibition of medication with prohibited substances, including alcohol. The majority of jurists have inferred that it is not permissible to use alcohol according to the honorable Sunnah: among them is the hadith narrated by Tariq bin Suwaid Al-Ja'fi that he asked the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, about alcohol, and he forbade it or disliked making it, so he said: I only make it for medicine. This hadith indicates an explicit indication that it is not permissible to treat with wine and that it is forbidden by Sharia, and that saying or claiming that it is a medicine is rejected by the explicit saying of the Prophet, peace and blessings of God be upon him: "It is not a medicine but a disease." And the disease is disease and illness, and that is because God Almighty robbed wine of its benefits when It is forbidden, and what the Noble Qur'an indicates that it has benefits for people, it is before it is prohibited, and if the benefit remains, then its prohibition is definite, and the occurrence of healing by it is suspected, and the suspect is not able to remove the lump with it, which is the ruling of prohibition.

The hadith of Abu al-Darda' previously mentioned, which is that the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, said: "God has sent down the disease and the remedy and has made for every disease a remedy, so treat yourself and do not seek treatment with things that are forbidden." The hadith indicates what the first hadith indicated about the inadmissibility of medication with alcohol, and Imam Muhammad ibn al-Hasan al-Shaibani al-Hanafi inferred the inadmissibility of medication with alcohol, according to what was narrated on the authority of Aisha, may God be pleased with her, that the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, said: "I do not intoxicate much of it." So a little of it is forbidden." And he said: "Every intoxicant made from grape juice is called wine, because it is a drink of the mind, and the meaning of intoxicating is found in all other intoxicating drinks." And it was stated in the kit, the explanation of the mayor: "It is not permissible to take medication with forbidden" and in the fatwas of Ibn Taymiyyah, and he was asked about medication with wine. And pork and other taboos, is it permissible out of necessity? He said, may God have mercy on him: "It is not permissible to take medication with that." With a similar answer, Ibn al-Qayyim said in Zad al-Ma'ad, and with a similar answer, Abu Bakr Ibn al-Arabi al-Maliki went to it in his book Ahkam al-Qur'an, after he mentioned the words of Sahfoon: He does not use it - that is, alcohol - under any circumstances or with pork.

The second doctrine:

And it is the doctrine that permits treatment with forbidden things, including alcohol, and those who went to that Imam Abu Hanifa, may God be pleased with him and his companion Abu Yusuf, and a saying of Imam Shafi'i and Al-Zahiriya - and they said that it is permissible to drink alcohol for treatment with it, taking into account the case of necessity. Imam al-Kasani said in his Badaa': "And seeking treatment with the forbidden is permissible when it is certain that a cure will take place in it, such as eating dead dead when hungry, wine when thirsty, and drinking a mouthful of food. Ibn Hazm al-Dhahiri said: "Wine is permissible for those who are forced into it, so whoever is forced to drink wine for thirst or as a remedy or to ward off suffocation and drink it, then there is no limit for him." His argument in this is that medication is considered one of the cases of necessity, and necessities allow prohibitions. In this, Ibn Hazm al-Zahiri says: Medication is a matter of necessity, and God Almighty said: (ثُمَّ ذُنُوبٌ يُبَيِّنُ). Except for the necessity of medication and the like, with evidence that the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, used the urine of camels as a means of treatment for disease, and the first hadiths that were mentioned by the doctrine

that prevents that. And he said, "Next to it, if it is necessary to take medication with it, and thus it is permissible, so it is not one of the evils in the case of necessity." As for the Shafi'is, they differentiate between alcohol and other forbidden things. For them, it is permissible to treat with impurities and all other taboos except for alcohol. The Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, who was narrated by Anas, may God be pleased with him, and his text: "A group of 'Uraynah – the tribe of 'Uraynah – came to the Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, and pledged allegiance to him upon Islam. You go out to our shepherd in his camels, so you will be infected with their urine and milk. They said: indeed. So they went out and drank of its milk and urine, so they recovered." It is clear from this inference that the Shafi'is measured impurities and all other taboos - except for wine - on the urine of camels, which are impure according to them, in the permissibility of treatment with them. As for wine, they said that it is permissible to drink it in order to sweeten a morsel if he does not find something to sweeten it with pure liquids, they said that if he drenched in a morsel and did not find anything to drink it with it except wine, then he is allowed to drink it without disagreement. He has this reasoning, justifying this obligation by saying that safety from death is by this desirability, a break unlike medication and drinking it for thirst, but they differed in the permissibility of medication with wine and other intoxicants, as the majority of them do not permit medication with it, and their argument is the hadith narrated by Muslim in his Sahih.

And some of them allow treatment with it, and the argument for this hatred is the analogy with the permissibility of drinking camel urine for some sick Bedouins from the Arina tribe, which is proven by the hadith of the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, which was narrated by Anas and we mentioned it. As for Imam Abu Hanifa and his companion Abu Yusuf, they inferred the permissibility of drinking alcohol for medicinal purposes, taking into account the state of necessity by the following:

First: A hadith on the authority of the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace. Al-Tahawi mentioned on the authority of Abdullah bin Omar and Ibn Masoud, may God be pleased with them, that the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, came with wine, then he smelled it and cut his face because of its severity, then called for water and poured it on him and drank from it.

Second, the effects:

- 1- It was narrated on the authority of Umar, may God be pleased with him, that he used to drink heavy wine and say: We will slaughter the camels, and the freeing of them belongs to the family of Omar, and only strong wine can cut it.
- 2- It was narrated that Omar wrote to Ammar bin Yasir, may God be pleased with them, that I came from Syria with a cooking drink, until two-thirds of it was gone, and one-third remained.

Our preferred opinion:

To clarify the correct statement, two issues are necessary:

First: Does the condition of the disease enter the extent of necessity? And if the answer is in the affirmative, then does the prohibited medication become permissible, just as the necessity of the product permits the eating of dead meat and the like.

The second: What is the significance of the honorable hadiths that were invoked by those who prevented them?

As for the first issue. It can be said that the state of the disease in which the patient fears death is included in the meaning of necessity. Al-Shafi'i, may God have mercy on him, said: "It was said that there is a second aspect of necessity, for a man to fall ill with the disease that the people of knowledge tell him about, or he is one of the people of knowledge about it: He who is like this rarely recovers except that he eats this or drinks such and that, or it is said to him that The quickest thing that clears you is eating such-and-drinking such-and-such, then he will have the right to eat and drink that unless it is alcohol if he swallows something that intoxicates him, or something that takes the mind away from the taboos or other things. To say that what is forbidden according to Imam al-Shafi'i is to take the amount that intoxicates, not the amount that does not. As for the statement of the authorized, it seems to me that it is predicated on its release, that is, on the amount that intoxicates and does not intoxicate. It cannot be imposed on restriction, i.e. on the amount that does not intoxicate.. It takes from the saying of Al-Shafi'i that the state of illness is considered one of the cases of necessity, and it is not weakened by the word "said" because Al-Shafi'i, may God have mercy on him, was satisfied with what was said, with evidence that he did not comment on it and did not object to it. In fact, al-Shafi'i made it necessary for the condition of a disease from which recovery is delayed when one does not eat forbidden things. Also, we have presented in the definition of necessity: "It is the urgent state of eating what is forbidden by Sharia".

There is no doubt that the state of illness is a state that is forced to eat what is forbidden by Sharia. Because if the patient is not treated, it is feared that the disease will increase, weakness and death. And the fear of that makes sickness a state of necessity. The jurist Ibn Hazm said: "The limit of necessity is that he stays for a day and night in which he does not find anything to eat or drink, and he fears the harmful weakness that goes too far and leads to death." So if the limit of necessity does not lead to the death of a person immediately, if he does not deal with the forbidden Rather, it also includes the weakness that afflicts the compelled, and this weakness increases by his abandoning the prohibition until this weakness delivers him to destruction. Our statement is supported by what the owner of Al-Mughni said: "The legal necessity is that which he fears will be damaged if he abandons eating. Ahmad said: If he fears for himself, whether it is from hunger or fears, if he gives up eating he is unable to walk and is cut off from companionship, then he perishes or he is unable to ride, and he will perish." ...".

As for the second issue, which is the significance of the noble hadiths that were invoked by the objectors, these hadiths are authentic and no one can doubt their authenticity. But its indication of prohibition is not a conclusive indication, as it can be interpreted other than in the case of necessity, that there is a permissible medicine that takes the place of the prohibited period and takes its place. Especially if there is a necessity. Moreover, it is permissible to drink wine in a state of extreme and fatal thirst - according to the opinion that we prefer - and to drink it to remove a lump by the agreement of the fuqaha', and it is permissible to take alcohol by syringe in surgical operations so that the patient does not feel the pain of the surgery. Therefore, the opinion that I prefer and lean towards, is that the state of illness falls within the meaning of necessity and is considered one of its states, and as long as it is a state of necessity, it permits the prohibited, as there is no difference between necessity and necessity, as long as the meaning of having to prohibit is present in them. This is supported by the fact that God, the Blessed and Most high, said: (تَبَّ تَبَّ) the Lord, Blessed and Exalted be He, excluded prohibitions from prohibition and prohibition in case of necessity, and did not separate and did not restrict necessity by necessity without necessity, such as hunger and thirst. Therefore, it should be carried at all, and the necessity of prohibiting it for the purpose of medication is included. In conclusion, what we prefer is the permissibility of prohibitions in medicine, but with conditions including: that the disease be frightening, i.e. fatal, and that there is no permissible medicine that takes the place of the prohibited medicine, and that the people of knowledge of medicine indicate that this medicine leads to recovery in most cases, and that taking it is as much as it is rushing. It is necessary in case of illness, even if he asks for a period of medication, and if it is available. These conditions we took the case of necessity and the saying of the legal jurists for that. And the license that God authorized for his weak servants. God knows.

The third requirement: the use of the organs of the dead in treating the living

There may be a necessity to use the organs of the deceased in the treatment of the patient, such as grafting the cornea of the eye of a living person with the cornea of a newly-dead person, or by removing any other part of the deceased and using it in the treatment of a patient for whom there is the fear of death or damage to one of his organs. Is this permissible due to the necessity of the disease or not? .?

Know that what is meant by the dead here is the one whose soul departed from his body by completely cutting off from his body, from the stopping of the beating of his heart naturally or artificially, and the completion of his emirate. , shrouding him, praying for him and burying him. As for setting up "brain death, or the brain stem" in order to achieve his death with his heartbeat, even if mechanically, this is in fact not death, but rather a harbinger of death, as it still has the rule of the living until the soul is separated from the body.

As for the use of the organs of the deceased, a dispute arose among the jurists in this regard, like any other subject in question. But before we talk about this issue, we clarify a ruling if a person is forced to eat human flesh. Some scholars have permitted if this human blood is permissible, such as the warrior and the apostate, for a person to kill him and eat from him as much as necessary. Ibn Qudamah said in *Al-Mughni*: "And if blood is permissible, such as the warrior and the apostate, then the judge mentioned that killing and eating him is permissible because killing him is permissible. And this is what the companions of *Al-Shafi'i* said, because it is not forbidden for him, then he is like a carnivore. And if he finds an infallible dead person, it is not permissible to eat it according to our companions, and *Al-Shafi'i* and some of the Hanafis said that it is permissible and it is better because the sanctity of the living is greater. *Abu Al-Khattab* chose to eat it and said: There is no argument in this hadith here, because eating from meat, not from bones, and what is meant by the hadith is an analogy in the origin of the sanctity, not in its amount, as evidenced by their difference in security and retribution and the obligation to protect the living with what is not obligatory to protect the dead. This is the text of *Ibn Qudamah al-Hanbali's* words regarding the killing of the infallible with the intent of eating it or eating from the dead infallible blood. As for the *Shafi'i* jurists, they permitted eating from the dead if he did not find another. It was stated in *Mughni al-Muhtaaj*: "And he who is forced to eat a dead human being if he does not find another dead person.. because the sanctity of the living is greater than the sanctity of the dead, except if the dead is a prophet, then it is not permissible." Eating from it is definite - as *Ibrahim al-Marwazi* said and approved it, and whether the deceased is a Muslim and the one in need is an infidel, it is not permissible to eat from it for the honor of Islam.

By looking and without going into more details, it becomes clear to us that it is permissible - in the opinion of some - to eat from a dead person in a state of necessity, and that is to preserve the life of a living person, because the sanctity of the living and keeping it is greater than the sanctity of the dead, and accordingly, the jurists were divided on the issue of benefit. Forced into parts of the human body in the event of having to make two opinions:

The first opinion: The Hanafis, Malikis - in contrast to *Ibn Abd al-Salam* - and *al-Zahiriyya*, view the inadmissibility of using parts of the dead, in order to prevent the violation of the sanctity of the human being. And for his saying, may God's prayers and peace be upon him: "Breaking the bone of the dead is like breaking the bone of the living."

The second opinion: The majority of jurists - some Hanafis, some Malikis, *Shafi'is*, Hanbalis and *Zaydis* - view the permissibility of using parts of a dead person, and they justified this by the fact that the sanctity of a living human being is greater than the sanctity of the dead.

However, it is necessary for us to visualize the conditions so that, by God's permission, the lawful reality is revealed to the natural, realistic reality of every issue concerning it. Here are two extremes: dead and alive. As for the dead person who was taken from it: We imagine the situation in terms of permission and lack of it as follows:

- 1- A dead person had given permission before his death to remove an organ from him for a specific or unspecified one.
- 2- The deceased did not make an heir.
- 3- He died after an heir, and the heir did not give permission.
- 4- He died after heirs, so some gave permission.
- 5- He died after heirs, so they were all authorized.

As for the neighborhood, its interests are not devoid of three levels of interests:

- 1- Either it is necessary, his life depends on that.
- 2- Or she is a need on which his life does not depend.
- 3- Or it could be an improvement in terms of luxuries.

If it is necessary, and what is necessary here is explained by what his life depends on, such as the heart, kidneys, lungs and the like from the necessary principles of benefit, they said permissibility and the permissibility comes out - according to the one who said it, which is the public - for many things, including:

- A- By balancing the interests and evils, and the benefits and harms, the interest of the living by taking care of saving a life is greater than the interest of the dead by violating the sanctity of his body when the soul has left him and authorized him. This has analogues in the branches of jurisprudence scattered by a number of scholars from eating in case of necessity, such as: milk of a dead woman, eating human flesh, slitting the abdomen of a pregnant dead woman if her pregnancy is hopeful for his life, exhuming the grave for the benefit of a living person, and a dead stomach that swallowed living money to the last of what Advance from the consequential or branching branches on the basis of the most severe harm is removed by the lesser harm, or chooses the lesser of two evils or the lesser of two harms, or a rule if two evils contradict each other, the greatest harm being taken into account by the lesser of them. All this has been explained in detail before.
- B- And the condition of the permission of the deceased or the permission of his heirs, because taking care of his dignity is a right established for him in the Shari'a and is not violated except with his permission. It is forbidden after his death within the limits of what he authorized, and therefore the condition of his permission is required before his death, or from all of his heirs. And his guardian is the place of his heir.

The most correct opinion:-

This and the opinion that I tend to and which I prefer, is that it is permissible to make use of the parts of the dead when necessary, whether he is infallible or not, with the aim of reviving The human soul and the extension of reasons for its survival. Especially since the dead soul, if not benefited from it, dissolves and becomes dust, so saving a living soul with something from a dead soul is to preserve the soul and revive it, is a legitimate goal, and a legitimately established, and reliable interest, in addition to the fact that taking care of the interest of the living in the extension of his life, is more important than taking care of the interest The dead in not touching his body, as his body is decomposing and perishing, but this cannot be done unless conditions are fulfilled in this matter. These conditions are:

- 1- Achieving necessity by means of certainty, by any indication that certainty can provide, such as the news of a skilled doctor, and it is not required that he be a Muslim.
- 2- Achieving the confinement of medication to it, because there is no alternative for it to take its place and perform its function efficiently.
- 3- The operation should be performed by a skilled, educated and skilled doctor.
- 4- The preponderance of conjecture that it will succeed in the forced to whom it is transferred.
- 5- That this be done with the intent of necessity and not to exceed the required amount.
- 6- Availability of the process requirements that medicine has reached, otherwise the doctor is excessive and bears the penalty for his negligence.
- 7- That the compelled person should be infallible in blood, because if he was deserving of killing according to Sharia, then his blood would be infallible, and his life would end with the implementation of the Sharia ruling in it, and therefore it is not permissible in Shariah to work on extending the causes of his life.
- 8- There should be permission to use the parts of the dead person, and this permission may be issued by the deceased before his death, given that he has guardianship over himself, or issued by his heirs after his death, and they are the ones who have the right to the inheritance left by him according to Sharia.
- 9- There is no other death than the human death. If another death is found, it is not permissible to benefit from the human death.

This was approved by the Council of the Islamic Fiqh Council held during its fourth conference session in Jeddah in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia from 18 to 23 Jumada al-Akhirah 1408 AH corresponding to 11/6/1988. With the organs of another human being, whether alive or dead." I acknowledge the topic we are dealing with, which is "the use of the organs of the dead to treat the living" in case of necessity.

The most important results:

- In the event of illness for the purposes of examination and treatment, it is permissible to examine the return and the doctor's examination, except for what it is not permissible for him to look at from the body of a woman or a man for

necessity, but the necessity is estimated according to its extent with regard to examination, examination, palpation by hand, and other requirements of examination and treatment.

- This permission and licensing should not be granted in the treatment of women by the man and the treatment of men by the woman, unless there is no woman who knows about medicine and treatment.
- There is no disease in which alcohol is used as a cure, unless instead of alcohol there is another medicine that takes its place, and is saved from its bad consequences.
- There is no disease in which alcohol is used as a cure, unless instead of alcohol there is another medicine that takes its place, and is saved from its bad consequences.
- A group of many jurists went to the prohibition of drug treatment with taboos, whether it is from food or drink, especially alcohol.
- Permissibility of using the parts of the dead when necessary, whether infallible or not, with the aim of reviving the human soul and extending the reasons for its survival.

Margins:

- () Fath al-Bari with the explanation of Sahih al-Bukhari by Ibn Hajar al-Asqalani, volume 10, p. 168, a footnote to the response of al-Mukhtar to al-Durr al-Mukhtar, Sharh Tanweer al-Absar by Ibn Abdeen, volume 5, p. 244, The Yemeni Press in Egypt.
- () The analogies and isotopes of Al-Suyuti, p. 60.
- () Al-Mabsoot by Abu Bakr Muhammad bin Abi Sahl Al-Sarkhi, edition of the year 1314 AH, Al-Sa'ada Press in Egypt, vol.10, p. 156.
- () Indian Fatwas, authored by a group of Indian scholars, printed by Bulaq Press in Egypt in the year 1310 AH, AH 5, p. 342 and thereafter.
- () Al-Hedaya Explanation of the Beginning of the Beginner by Abu Al-Hasan Ali bin Abi Bakr Al-Mughinani, last edition, volume 4, p. 84.
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- () Al-Mughni by Ibn Qudamah al-Hanbali, Volume 8, pg. 365 and beyond, as well as al-Uddah, Sharh al-Umda Baha al-Din Abd al-Rahman al-Maqdisi al-Hanbali, p. 586.
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- () Verse 119 of Surat Al-An'am.
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- () Previous reference p. 50, p. 51.
- () Explanation of the Meanings of Al-Athar by Al-Tahawi, Volume 4, p. 219, Edited by Muhammad Zuhri Al-Najjar.
- () See the details of this issue d. Faraj Zahran in intoxicants, its harms and provisions, p. 156.
- () The Mother of Muhammad bin Idris al-Shafi'i, Volume 2, p. 253.

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- () Al-Shabah and Al-Nazaer by Ibn Najim Al-Hanafi, p. 89.
- () Dr. Hassan Ali Al-Shazly. In the ruling on transferring human organs in Islamic jurisprudence, p. 54.
- () See the Journal of Contemporary Fiqh Research - Issue Three - The First Year from Rabi' al-Akhir to Jumada al-Akhirah 1410 AH, November - December - January 1990, p. 220.

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